

1 **Prospective Computational Design and *In Vitro* Bio-Analytical Tests of New Chemical**
2 **Entities as Potential Selective CYP17A1 Lyase Inhibitors**

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17 **ABSTRACT**

18 The development and advancement of prostate cancer (PCa) into stage 4, where it metastasize,
19 is a major problem mostly in elder males. The growth of PCa cells is stirred up by androgens
20 and androgen receptor (AR). Therefore, therapeutic strategies such as blocking androgens
21 synthesis and inhibiting AR binding have been explored in recent years. However, recently
22 approved drugs (or in clinical phase) failed in improving the expected survival rates for this
23 metastatic-castration resistant prostate cancer (mCRPC) patients. The selective CYP17A1

24 inhibition of 17,20-lyase route has emerged as a novel strategy. Such inhibition blocks the
25 production of androgens everywhere they are found in the body. In this work, a three
26 dimensional-quantitative structure activity relationship (3D-QSAR) pharmacophore model is
27 developed on a diverse set of non-steroidal inhibitors of CYP17A1 enzyme. Highly active
28 compounds are selected to define a six-point pharmacophore hypothesis with a unique
29 geometrical arrangement fitting the following description: two hydrogen bond acceptors (A),
30 two hydrogen bond donors (D) and two aromatic rings (R). The QSAR model showed adequate
31 predictive statistics. The 3D-QSAR model is further used for database virtual screening of
32 potential inhibitory hit structures. Density functional theory (DFT) optimization provides the
33 electronic properties explaining the reactivity of the hits. Docking simulations discovers
34 hydrogen bonding and hydrophobic interactions as responsible for the binding affinities of hits
35 to the CYP17A1 Protein Data Bank structure. 13 hits from the database search (including five
36 derivatives) are then synthesized in the laboratory as different scaffolds. Ultra high
37 performance liquid chromatography-tandem mass spectrometry (UHPLC-MS/MS) *in vitro*
38 experiments reveals three new chemical entities (NCEs) with half maximal inhibitory
39 concentration (IC_{50}) values against the lyase route at mid-micromolar range with favorable
40 selectivity to the lyase over the hydroxylase route (one of them with null hydroxylase
41 inhibition). Thus, prospective computational design has enabled the design of potential lead
42 lyase-selective inhibitors for further studies.

43 **Keywords:** metastatic-castration resistant prostate cancer; 3D-QSAR pharmacophore model;
44 CYP17A1 inhibitors; 17,20-lyase selective inhibition; Prospective computational design

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48 Author Contributions

49 The authors contributed equally. All authors have given approval to the final version of the
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51 Conflict of interest

52 NJG is the registered inventor on the two patents that are pending in national and regional phases:
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55 financial support for this work that could have influenced its outcome.

56 ABBREVIATIONS

57 NCE, New Chemical Entity; UHPLC, Ultra-High Performance Liquid Chromatography;
58 APCI, Atmospheric Pressure Chemical Ionization; Abiraterone Acetate, AA; Abiraterone,
59 ABT; MRM, Multiple Reaction Monitoring; 3D-QSAR, 3 Dimensional Quantitative Structure
60 Activity Relationship; IFD; Induced Fit Docking; CPH; Common Pharmacophore Hypothesis;
61 DFT, Density Functional Theory; PLS, Partial Least Squares; mCRPC, Metastatic castration
62 resistant prostate cancer.

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66

67 1. INTRODUCTION

68 Prostate cancer (PCa) has emerged as a real danger in elderly male because it is able to
69 develop, grow, relapse and then metastasize [1-7]. The androgens are very important in the
70 biological processes of normal and diseased prostates [1,8]. First in line therapy to treat PCa
71 includes the use of antiandrogens (i.e. the chemotherapeutic agent docetaxel) as well as the
72 analogues of gonadotropin releasing hormone in combination with androgen receptor (AR)
73 antagonists [9-11]. All these treatment options proved futile in the blockage of androgen
74 biosynthesis in all its sources such as the testes and adrenals [12]. The progression of
75 metastatic-castration resistant prostate cancer (mCRPC) is lethal and aggressive; so, there is a
76 great demand to find alternative treatment options in pursuit to increase the overall survival
77 rates of patients suffering from mCRPC [13].

78 The use of CYP17A1 enzyme as a drug target is an attractive option [14-18]. Its
79 inhibition decreases the levels of circulating androgens, which is thought to be more effective
80 than conventional therapies [1,10,14-20]. The CYP17A1 enzyme is responsible for the
81 catalysis and conversion of progesterone and pregnenolone into 17 α -products, such as 17 α -
82 hydroxyprogesterone and 17 α -hydroxypregnenolone, respectively [4,21,22]. The hydroxylase
83 route is important in cortisol formation. Thus, the inhibition of the formation of cortisol results
84 in mineralocorticoid excess syndrome (MES), which is associated with cardiovascular diseases
85 [20,23]. Bird et al. [24] have pointed out that in humans the role of CYP17A1 is also to catalyze
86 the conversion of 17 α -hydroxypregnenolone to form dehydroepiandrosterone (DHEA) through
87 the lyase route. Since the lyase route does not undergo MES [20,23], the design of CYP17A1
88 inhibitors with favorable lyase selectivity over hydroxylase is a promising therapeutic strategy
89 [9,25].

90 Ketoconazole (KTZ) is an antifungal agent currently used as an off-label drug for PCa
91 therapy targeting the CYP17A1 enzyme [26]. However, its therapeutic effect is outweighed by

92 its toxicity effect [9,27]. Abiraterone (ABT) was discovered and designed to improve the
93 overall survival rates of patients suffering from mCRPC [26]. Abiraterone acetate (AA)
94 attained its approval in 2011 by the US Food and Drug Administration [9,22,26]. The main
95 drawback regarding AA is the dual inhibition of both the 17α -hydroxylase and the 17,20-lyase
96 routes of CYP17A1 enzyme [23]. Hence, patients on the AA therapy are also given prednisone
97 in order to account for MES [9,13,19,28].

98 The non-steroidal inhibitors such as orteronel (TAK-700) [28], galeterone (TOK001)
99 [26,27,29,30] and seviteronel (VT-464) [23,31] selectively inhibit the lyase route over the
100 hydroxylase of CYP17A1 enzyme; according to pre-clinical data [9,26]. The Phase III clinical
101 trials for orteronel and galeterone were halted due to a lack of therapeutic benefits outweighing
102 those of the current medications in the clinic for these agents [31-34]. Seviteronel on the other
103 hand, is presently undergoing Phase II clinical trials for both prostate and breast cancer [23,31].
104 Pharmacodynamics data for seviteronel has revealed that this drug is a selective 17,20-lyase
105 inhibitor [25,24]. *In vitro* experimental data has revealed a half maximal inhibitory
106 concentration (IC_{50}) of 670 and 69 nM for 17α -hydroxylase and 17,20-lyase inhibition,
107 respectively [23].

108 Prospective computational design of novel compounds has enabled the ability to
109 explain the interactions at molecular level and to predict biological activities of novel
110 molecules from their structural properties prior to laboratory testing [31]. Purushottamachar et
111 al. [32] performed a qualitative 3D pharmacophore model for well-known natural AR down-
112 regulating agents, which was subsequently followed by a database search and synthesis of
113 potential AR inhibitors. Furthermore, Gianti et al. [5] used induced-fit docking on CYP17A1
114 inhibitors on a homology model of CYP17A1, since the X-ray crystal structure of the
115 CYP17A1 enzyme was unavailable. In 2012, two crystal structures of CYP17A1 co-crystallized
116 with CYP17 inhibitors ABT (3RUK) and galeterone (3SWZ) were deposited into the Protein

117 Data Bank (PDB) [23]. This has paved the way for prospective computational design of new
118 inhibitor drugs. However, the absence of cytochrome b5 bound to CYP17A1 enzyme in current
119 PDB structures still limits modeling the effects of 17,20-lyase inhibition [19,20,21]. Recently,
120 a virtual screening work-flow combined with density functional theory (DFT) and docking on
121 the CYP17A1 structure (3SWZ) was used to identify two potential inhibitors for the CYP17A1
122 enzyme; however, the downside was that a further inhibition assay revealed that they were not
123 selective to the 17,20-lyase route [33].

124 There is a great need for third generation antiandrogens that are selective 17,20-lyase
125 inhibitors to treat mCRPC. The main idea is to design drugs that would improve the survival
126 rates of ~5 months that is offered by current medications to 2-5 years. In this work,
127 pharmacophore modelling from non-steroidal CYP17A1 inhibitors was used as a ligand-based
128 drug design (LBDD) approach, as a concrete form of molecular characteristics (spatial
129 distribution of groups) that are essential for molecular realization of a ligand by a protein,
130 receptor or enzyme [32,35,36]. The subsequent pharmacophore hypothesis was further used
131 for a database screening and the selection of hit structures with potential inhibitory capability.
132 Density functional theory [37] was then used to deduce their electronic properties. Lastly,
133 molecular docking was used as a structure-based drug design (SBDD) strategy to reveal the
134 binding mode of hit structures in the active site cavity of CYP17A1 enzyme. Therefore, LBDD
135 and SBDD approaches complement each other [38]. The selected hits from these approaches
136 showing good binding to CYP17A1 enzyme were synthesized as new chemical entities (NCEs)
137 and their IC_{50} values against hydroxylase and lyase routes were measured by bioanalytical tests
138 employing ultra high performance liquid chromatography-tandem mass spectrometry
139 (UHPLC-MS/MS).

140 The hypotheses used in this work are the following: (i) the development of novel,
141 effective and selective/secure anti-mCRPC compounds is a constant necessity. Thus, chemical

142 scaffolds different from the currently used in the clinic (with reduced success up to now) are
143 needed. They could be obtained combining *in-vitro* information on non-steroidal inhibitors
144 with computer aided drug design methods (pharmacophore model, database screening,
145 molecular docking for hit selection) (ii) Selective CYP17A1 17,20-lyase inhibitors should not
146 be based on homology models (due to the absence of the important amino acids in the active
147 site of the enzyme at molecular level [39,40]). Thus, the use of available 3RUK and 3SWZ
148 structures are preferable. The one showing best results with its co-crystallized ligands should
149 be selected. (iii) In a preliminary study of novel scaffolds, as in this case, the primary objective
150 is to find compounds showing high selective or virtually specific inhibition of the lyase route
151 (i.e. with null inhibition of the hydroxylase route).

152 2. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

153 2.1. Chemistry

154 Herein, we report, for the first time, the synthesis of 13 NCEs based on the scaffolds
155 depicted in scheme 1 to 9. The general procedures for the laboratory synthesis for compound
156 **1-8e** as shown in Table 2 is outlined.

158 **Scheme 1.** Reagents and conditions: (1) DMF, DIPEA, 3 hrs, 100 °C, 20%.

159 The synthesis of NCE **1** was performed by the addition of 2-(2-Mercapto-4-methyl-thiazol-
160 5-yl)-acetamide (compound **1**) to a mixture containing 2-Chloro-1-(1H-indol-3-yl)-2-phenyl-
161 ethanone (compound **2**) in N,N-Diisopropylethylamine (Hünig's base) and
162 Dimethylformamide (DMF) solvent. A yield of 20% was obtained for NCE **1**.

163

164 **Scheme 2.** Reagents and conditions: (1) DMF, DIPEA, 3 hrs, 100 °C, 20%.

165 The synthesis of NCE 2 was performed by adding 4-Furan-2-ylmethyl-5-indol-3-ylidene-
 166 [1,2,4]triazolidene-3-thione (compound 3) to a mixture containing 2-Chloro-N-(2-chloro-
 167 benzyl)-acetamide (compound 4) in N,N-Diisopropylethylamine (Hünig's base) and
 168 Dimethylformamide (DMF) solvent. A yield of 20% was obtained for NCE 2.

169

170 **Scheme 3.** Reagents and conditions: (1) acetic acid, sodium acetate, 100 °C for 8hrs, 48%.

171 Commercially available 2-Cyano-N-(4-ethylphenyl)-acetamide (compound 5) was
 172 reacted with 6-Methoxy-4-oxo-4H-chromene-3-carbaldehyde (compound 6) in a solution
 173 containing acetic acid and sodium acetate. Coupling of the two compounds via N-
 174 acylation and subsequent rearrangements of the amine. Crystallization of the resulting
 175 precipitate with acetonitrile gave a 48% yield of the tautomer of NCE 3.

176

177 **Scheme 4.** Reagents and conditions: (1) DMF, DIPEA, 1hr. (2) 6hrs at 100 °C, 50%.

178 The synthesis of NCE 4 was performed by coupling 2-Amino-3-methyl-benzoic acid
179 (compound 7) with 4-(2-Bromo-ethoxy)-benzenesulfonamide (compound 8) in N,N-
180 Diisopropylethylamine (Hünig's base) and Dimethylformamide (DMF) solvent. A yield of
181 50% was obtained.

183 **Scheme 5.** Reagents and conditions: (1) DIPEA, potassium iodide (catalyst), DMF, boiling water bath for 5 min
184 (2) 6hrs at 100 °C, 30%.

185 The N-acylation of m-aminophenyl-2-methoxypropanamide (compound 9) and
186 benzylchloridemethanamide (compound 10) was undertaken by the addition of Hünig's base
187 N,N-Diisopropylethylamine (DIPEA) and potassium iodide as a catalyst. The resulting NCE 5
188 was obtained in 30% yield.

190 **Scheme 6.** Reagents and conditions: (1) DIPEA, DMF, 100 °C for 1 hr (2) 100 °C for 6 hrs, 50%.

191 The synthesis of NCE 6 was performed by a coupling reaction of 1H-Indazole-3-
192 carboxylic acid (compound 11) with N-[4-(2-Chloro-propionyl)-phenyl]-butyramide
193 (compound 12), by using N,N-Diisopropylethylamine (Hünig's base) and Dimethylformamide
194 (DMF) solvent. A yield of 50% was obtained.

195

196

197 **Scheme 7.** Reagents and conditions: (1) THF, triethylamine, t-butylchloroformate, -78 °C. (2) NaOH, THF, 2
 198 hrs, 91%.

199 Synthesis of NCE 7 was performed by using a commercially available 4-oxo-bis-benzoic
 200 acid (compound 13) as a starting material; and was added to a solution containing
 201 Tetrahydrofuran (THF), triethylamine, and t-butylchloroformate. To the resulting solution 4-
 202 aminoisobutyric acid (compound 14) was then added and NaOH in cold water for
 203 heterocyclization and N-acylation. Then recrystallization of the resulting precipitate
 204 yielded 91% of NCE 7.

205

R = Cl (a)

R = OH (b)

R = H (c)

R = H (d)

R = Cl (e)

206

207 **Scheme 8.** Reagents and conditions: (1) methanol, 58-60 °C for 60-90 min. (2) acetonitrile, sodium borohydride,
208 0 °C. (3) sonication for 2 hrs at room temperature. (4) stand overnight at room temperature, 74-92%. Where: **(a)**
209 NCE 8, **(b)** NCE 8a, **(c)** NCE 8b, **(d)** NCE 8c, and **(e)** NCE 8e.

210 The synthesis of NCE **8** was performed by reacting [(6-hydroxy-3-oxo-3,4-dihydro-
211 benzoxazin)]-7-amine with the commercially available (3-formyl)pyridin-3-ylbenzamide
212 compound **16b** was performed in anhydrous ethanol. The reaction starts with reductive
213 amination, followed by the reduction of the imine product that forms. The reaction was allowed
214 to stand overnight at room temperature and purification was performed to yield 74-92% of
215 compound **8**, **8a - 8e**.

217 **Scheme 9.** Reagents and conditions: (1) anhydrous dichloromethane, triethylamine, room temperature for 14
218 hours (2) ethyl acetate, 99%.

219 The synthesis of NCE **8d** was performed in 2 steps. The N-acylation reaction of compound
220 **15c** with readily available starting compound **17** was performed by adding the two reagents in
221 anhydrous dichloromethane and triethylamine,. This then gave 99% yield of NCE **8d**.

222 2.2. Design of the 3D-pharmacophore model

223 Table 1 shows the 78 studied inhibitors of CYP17A1 enzyme with *in vitro* experimental
224 IC_{50} collected from the literature [2, 9, 13, 19, 28, 41-43]. The 12 highest active training
225 compounds in Table 1 (ID 1, 2, 4, 7, 9-16) were used to define the CPHs. This data set includes
226 the non-steroidal drug orteronel (TAK700; ID 10), which has been suggested as a lyase
227 inhibitor [9,27]. 36 different six-point common pharmacophore hypotheses (CPHs) were
228 generated by PHASE (Table S1 in Supporting Information shows 12 CPHs including the best

229 one selected). A 3D-QSAR pharmacophore model was generated for each CPH by using all
 230 the training compounds in Table 1. All the models were statistically significant (p -values \ll
 231 0.05), indicating their reliability [44]. The best CPHs (AADDRR.860; No. 12 in Table S1) was
 232 selected according to their best overall predictive ability considering all the compounds in
 233 Table 1 ($R^2 = 0.92$, for training, and $Q^2 = 0.89$, for test compounds, using a 3 latent variables-
 234 PLS 3D-QSAR model; see other statistics in Table S1).

235

236 **Table 1.** Non-steroidal compounds (except ID 31) used for pharmacophore modelling.

ID	Name	Class	Subset	Sites		Fitness	IC_{50}	pIC_{50}	$epIC_{50}$ - 3LV
				matched	Ligand sites				
1	3d [28]	1	1	5	A1 A2 D- D3 R7 R6	0.9	13	7.89	7.46
2	1 [41]	2	1	6	A1 A3 D4 D6 R10 R11	1.0	16	7.80	7.45
3	5 [43]	3	2	4	A- A1 D- D3 R9 R8	1.7	18	7.74	7.55
4	(+)-3c [41]	1	1	6	A1 A3 D4 D5 R9 R8	0.8	19	7.72	7.61
5	13 [43]	3	2	4	A- A1 D- D3 R10 R9	1.7	19	7.72	7.50
6	24 [43]	3	2	6	A1 A3 D4 D5 R11 R12	3.0	21	7.68	7.67
7 ^[a]	17 [43]	3	1	6	A1 A3 D4 D5 R10 R11	3.0	24	7.62	7.70
8	15 [43]	3	2	4	A1 A- D3 D- R9 R10	2.0	27	7.57	7.38
9	16 [43]	3	1	4	A1 A- D3 D- R9 R10	2.0	28	7.55	7.37
	TAK700								
10 ^[b]	[28]	4	1	5	A1 A3 D5 D- R12 R13	0.9	28	7.55	7.81
11	3b [28]	1	1	6	A1 A3 D4 D5 R10 R9	1.1	29	7.54	6.98
12	7 [43]	3	1	4	A1 A- D3 D- R8 R9	2.0	33	7.48	7.48
13	26 [43]	3	1	6	A2 A4 D5 D6 R11 R12	2.6	36	7.44	7.57
14	16 [43]	3	1	4	A- A2 D- D5 R9 R8	1.5	37	7.43	7.12
15	32 [43]	3	1	6	A1 A3 D4 D5 R8 R9	2.6	38	7.42	7.4
16	33 [43]	3	1	6	A1 A3 D4 D5 R9 R10	2.9	40	7.40	7.54
17	22 [43]	3	1	6	A1 A3 D4 D5 R10 R11	2.5	44	7.36	7.45
18	34 [43]	3	2	6	A1 A3 D4 D5 R10 R9	2.6	45	7.35	7.36
19	14 [43]	3	1	4	A- A1 D- D3 R10 R9	1.7	49	7.31	7.44
20	9 [9]	5	1	4	A- A2 D- D5 R7 R6	1.5	52	7.28	7.16

21	9a [9]	5	1	3	A- A3 D- D- R7 R8	1.4	52	7.28	7.17
22	26 [2]	4	1	4	A- A2 D- D5 R7 R6	1.5	52	7.28	7.16
23	8 [43]	3	1	5	A1 A3 D4 D- R11 R10	1.1	54	7.27	7.13
24	13 [2]	4	1	3	A- A- D- D3 R7 R6	2.0	56	7.25	7.15
25	20 [28]	1	1	3	A- A- D3 D- R6 R7	1.2	64	7.19	7.43
26	6 [19]	6	2	5	A1 A3 D6 D- R15 R16	1.0	69	7.16	6.95
27	15 [2]	4	1	3	A- A- D3 D- R7 R8	1.2	75	7.12	7.43
28	22 [2]	4	1	3	A- A- D- D5 R9 R8	2.0	75	7.12	7.07
29	36 [43]	3	1	6	A1 A3 D4 D5 R8 R9	1.6	77	7.11	6.74
30	3i [28]	1	2	6	A1 A3 D4 D5 R12 R11	0.7	88	7.06	7.13
31 ^[e]	8 [9]	7	1	3	A- A- D- D3 R5 R6	1.8	97	7.01	7.02
32	24 [2]	4	1	3	A- A- D- D3 R5 R4	1.8	97	7.01	7.02
33	18 [41]	3	1	5	A1 A- D4 D5 R10 R11	1.8	120	6.92	7.06
34	6 [43]	3	1	5	A1 A3 D4 D- R11 R10	1.3	130	6.89	7.01
35	19 [28]	1	1	4	A- A3 D- D4 R8 R7	1.5	144	6.84	6.65
36	25 [43]	3	1	4	A2 A- D4 D- R10 R9	2.0	150	6.82	7.37
37	23 [43]	3	1	6	A1 A2 D5 D6 R11 R12	2.3	160	6.80	7.02
38	5ax [42]	8	1	4	A1 A- D2 D- R6 R5	1.4	170	6.77	6.77
39	2c [19]	6	2	4	A3 A2 D- D5 R12 R-	1.3	180	6.74	7.17
40	10 [9]	5	1	3	A- A- D- D3 R6 R5	1.5	186	6.73	6.66
41	14 [13]	9	1	3	A- A- D- D3 R7 R6	1.5	188	6.73	6.62
42	25 [2]	4	1	3	A- A- D- D3 R6 R5	1.5	186	6.73	6.80
43	3e [28]	1	1	6	A1 A3 D4 D5 R10 R9	0.7	190	6.72	6.61
44	11 [2]	4	1	3	A- A- D- D3 R6 R5	2.1	189	6.72	6.60
45	27 [2]	4	2	3	A- A- D- D2 R5 R4	2.0	226	6.65	6.71
46	30 [43]	3	1	3	A1 A- D- D- R7 R6	1.6	236	6.63	6.48
47	5ay [42]	8	1	3	A1 A- D2 D- R- R7	1.6	240	6.62	6.52
48	4 [9]	5	2	3	A- A- D- D3 R5 R6	1.4	248	6.61	6.71
49	5bx [43]	8	1	4	A1 A- D2 D- R6 R5	1.4	250	6.60	6.41
50	31 [43]	3	1	3	A1 A- D- D- R6 R5	1.7	263	6.58	6.45
51	3f [28]	1	2	6	A1 A3 D4 D5 R9 R10	0.5	290	6.54	6.62
52	13 [28]	1	1	4	A- A3 D- D4 R8 R7	1.5	307	6.51	6.65
53	2 [28]	1	1	4	A1 A- D3 D- R6 R8	1.1	333	6.48	6.27
54	28 [2]	4	1	3	A- A- D- D3 R7 R6	2.0	337	6.47	6.67
55	14 [2]	4	1	3	A- A- D- D3 R7 R6	1.4	343	6.46	6.60
56	27 [43]	3	2	3	A1 A- D- D- R5 R4	1.5	373	6.43	6.34
57	3g [28]	1	1	6	A1 A3 D4 D5 R10 R9	0.7	400	6.40	6.56

58	3j [28]	1	1	6	A1 A3 D4 D5 R8 R9	0.9	410	6.39	6.5
59	6 [28]	1	1	3	A2 A- D- D- R7 R9	1.6	423	6.37	6.25
60	25 [9]	5	1	3	A- A- D- D3 R5 R4	1.3	438	6.36	6.59
61	5 [28]	9	1	3	A2 A- D- D- R6 R8	1.6	587	6.23	6.21
62	29 [43]	3	1	3	A1 A- D- D- R6 R5	1.6	584	6.23	6.35
63	KTZ [2]	10	1	4	A3 A5 D- D- R10 R11	1.1	740	6.13	5.99
64	23 [9]	5	1	3	A- A- D- D2 R5 R4	1.5	760	6.12	6.33
65	12 [2]	4	1	3	A- A- D- D3 R6 R5	1.9	783	6.11	6.44
66	12 [9]	5	1	5	A3 A2 D- D4 R6 R5	2.1	876	6.05	6.13
67	28 [43]	3	1	3	A1 A- D- D- R5 R4	1.5	953	6.02	6.3
68	17 [9]	5	1	4	A3 A- D4 D- R6 R7	1.4	1370	5.86	5.94
69	13 [9]	5	2	4	A2 A- D4 D- R5 R6	1.6	1790	5.75	6.16
70	24 [9]	5	1	3	A2 A- D- D- R6 R5	1.2	2000	5.7	5.50
71	8 [28]	1	1	3	A1 A- D- D- R5 R6	1.1	2346	5.63	5.65
72	16 [9]	5	1	3	A2 A- D- D- R7 R6	1.1	3340	5.48	5.26
73	7 [28]	1	2	4	A3 A- D- D4 R10 R8	1.2	5000	5.3	6.02
74	10 [28]	1	1	3	A2 A- D- D- R7 R6	1.2	5000	5.3	5.19
75	4 [28]	1	1	4	A3 A- D- D4 R10 R8	1.1	10000	5.00	5.02
76	1 [28]	1	1	4	A1 A- D3 D- R6 R8	1.7	20000	4.7	4.93
77	3 [28]	1	2	4	A3 A- D- D4 R9 R7	1.2	20000	4.7	5.09
78	15 [28]	1	1	3	A1 A- D- D- R5 R6	1.3	20000	4.7	4.98

237 ^a Reference compound. ^b Orteronel. ^c Abiraterone analog (steroidal drug). ID = index. Name = code used in the original paper
238 (reference indicated). Class = chemical family (1: naphthylmethylimidazole; 2: naphthalene-2-carboxamide; 3:
239 biphenylmethylene 4-pyridine; 4: methylene imidazole substituted biaryls; 5: biphenylmethylenes; 6: 4-(1,2,3-triazole); 7:
240 abiraterone analog; 8: imidazolyl and triazolyl substituted biphenyl; 9: biphenylmethylimidazole; 10: Imidazole). Subset =
241 training (1) and test (2) for 3D-QSAR PLS model validation. Sites matched = Number of groups in the molecule fitting the
242 features of the pharmacophore. Fitness = fitness score (matching degree between the molecule and the best common
243 pharmacophore hypothesis). IC_{50} = half maximal inhibitory concentration. $pIC_{50} = -\log(IC_{50})$, used as response variable in the
244 3D-QSAR PLS model. $epIC_{50-3LV}$ = estimated pIC_{50} value from the PLS model with 3 latent variables. KTZ = ketoconazole
245 (ID 63). The Ligand sites column includes pharmacophore features (letters): hydrogen bond acceptors (A), hydrogen bond
246 donors (D) and aromatic rings (R), with the number of available site points of each type.

247

248 Figure 1 shows the estimated ($epIC_{50}$) vs. actual (pIC_{50}) data for all training and test
249 subsets in Table 1 for the 3D-QSAR model based on the best CPH. As can be seen, good

250 agreement between estimated and actual pIC_{50} values is observed, particularly for the most
251 potent compounds (with high pIC_{50}), which are of higher interest. It should be indicated that,
252 originally, 98 compounds were used (including 20 additional steroidal drugs). However, all
253 these extra compounds became outliers (i.e. they did not fit properly the CPHs or were badly
254 predicted by PLS), and were discarded. Only the compound ID 31 in Table 1, an AA analogue,
255 was not an outlier, and was retained for calculations. It was the only unique steroidal compound
256 used in this work.

257

258

259 **Figure 1.** Validation plot of the 3D-QSAR model based on the best common pharmacophore hypothesis (CPH)
260 showing the estimated versus the actual pIC_{50} values for the training (dot) and test (diamonds) compounds, subsets
261 1 and 2, respectively, in Table 1.

262

263 Table 1 shows the number of pharmacophore sites matched by each molecule as well
264 as the fitness scores (matching degree between the molecule and the best CPH). The molecule
265 ID = 7 in Table 1, with the highest fitness score (3.0), was selected as the reference compound.
266 Figure 2 shows the reference compound (IUPAC name: N-{4'-[1-hydroxy-1-(1H-imidazol-4-
267 yl)-2-methylpropyl][1,1'-biphenyl]-3-yl}acetamide) mapped onto the best CPH. It shows the

268 best CPH features, including two hydrogen bond acceptors (A1 and A3), two hydrogen bond
269 donors (D4 and D5) and two aromatic rings (R10 and R11). It also shows the point vectors
270 giving the direction where the amino acid residues of the enzyme will more likely form
271 hydrogen bonds with the ligand when bound to the target enzyme in its active site; identifying
272 the important characteristic features [45]. The reference molecule shows that the point vector
273 for the hydrogen bond acceptor (A3) is mapped onto the carbonyl group of N-methyl-2-
274 carboxamide. The hydrogen bond acceptor vector (A1) is mapped onto the nitrogen of the
275 imidazole ring. The hydrogen bond donor (D4) is mapped onto the OH group of the benzanol
276 moiety of the reference molecule. While the hydrogen bond donor vector (D5) is mapped onto
277 the N-H group of N-methyl-2-carboxamide moiety. The naphthalene rings (R10) and (R11),
278 respectively are properly aligned on the position where π - π interactions are most likely to occur
279 with aromatic rings of the amino acids of the enzyme.

280

281 **Figure 2.** Pharmacophore model with site point vectors of the best common pharmacophore hypothesis (CPH)
282 mapped onto the structure of the reference compound (ID 7 in Table 1). CPH: AADRRR. A = acceptor group; D
283 = donor group; R = aromatic ring.

284

285 **2.3. Pharmacophore database screening results**

286 2.5 million structures from the enamine database were evaluated. Those with
287 undesirable functional groups (from a toxicity point of view) and not satisfying the Lipinski's
288 rule of five were removed, reducing their number to 1 million. The predicted activities,
289 estimated from the 3D-QSAR model, provided 798 hit structures with $epIC_{50} > 7$ having the 6
290 pharmacophore sites of the best CPH. From them, the VSW provided a set of 20 hit structures,
291 which were submitted to geometry optimization using DFT and further docking study. Eight
292 hit structures, which were finally synthesized, are shown in Table 2 (Namely: **1-8**).

293 **2.4. Density functional theory results**

294 DFT calculations were also used to determine the electronic features of the hits. As an
295 example, Figure S1 (in Supporting Information) shows the results for NCE **1**. HOMO and
296 LUMO explains drug-receptor (electrons donating and accepting groups, respectively)
297 interactions as well as reactive (electrophiles or nucleophiles, respectively) functional groups
298 distribution [46]. The HOMO and LUMO spheres, mapped onto the (1H-indol-3-yl)-2-oxo and
299 [2-(1H-indol-3-yl)-2-oxo-1-phenylethyl] moieties, respectively, indicate the ability of NCE **1**
300 to donate and accept electrons, respectively, to appropriate amino acid residues of the receptor.
301 The energies observed for HOMO (-0.220 eV) and LUMO (-0.056 eV) orbitals shows a small
302 difference, which indicates that NCE **1** is reactive [47,48]. The HOMO-LUMO energy
303 differences for all the hits were in the range of 0.111 to 0.185 eV, indicating their reactivity.

304 The molecular electronic density shows two regions of low electronic density: the NH
305 group of the indole moiety as the hydrogen bond donor, and the NH₂ groups of the acetamide
306 moiety, as well as a region of high electronic density corresponding to electronegative carbonyl
307 groups (of the oxo and acetamide moieties). The MESP indicates the most electronegative
308 functional groups (the carbonyl groups of the phenyl-2-oxo and acetamide moieties, the N atom

309 of the thiazole moiety), as well as the least electronegative part (ring system). The obtained
310 isovalue of -57.380 kcal/mol for MESP mapped on NCE **1** after geometry optimization is
311 shown in Figure S1.

312 All of the electronic properties obtained by (DFT) indicate the reactive site of the hits
313 in relation to the selected AADRR860 3D-QSAR pharmacophore model and the relationship
314 between the structures and their reactivity.

315 **2.5. Molecular docking results**

316 The PDB enzyme structure 3SWZ was selected over 3RUK for further docking studies
317 because of its lower resolution and the consistent docking score and RMSD results, for both,
318 IFD and cross-docking stages (see Table S2 in Supporting Information). The galeterone
319 (TOK001) pose estimated by IFD docking was superimposed over the co-crystalized structure
320 of TOK001 in 3SWZ as a way to verify the performance of the docking process [49]. A high
321 degree of overlap between the two structures was found (see Figure S2 in Supporting
322 Information).

323 The 20 optimized hit structures were submitted to molecular docking. As an example,
324 Figure S3 (in Supporting Information) shows the resulting pose from IFD and the ligand
325 interaction diagram (LID) of NCE **1**. The binding mode for NCE **1** is an example of type I
326 inhibition, characterized by the absence of metal coordination between the indole N-
327 heterocyclic moiety and Fe³⁺ of ferric heme [25]. Type II inhibition is characterized by a metal
328 coordination between Fe³⁺ of the enzyme and the N-heterocycle of the ligand. Instead, in NCE
329 **1** there is a π - π interaction between the indole moiety of the molecule and the porphyrin moiety
330 of ferric heme of the enzyme (see Figure S3B). In addition, there are three hydrogen bonds
331 between: the NH group of the indole ring moiety and the carbonyl group of VAL482, the NH
332 group of the acetamide moiety and the carbonyl group of ASN202, and the carbonyl group of

333 the acetamide moiety and the NH group of ARG239. Finally, hydrophobic interactions
334 involved in this binding event includes (the involved CYP17A1 enzyme residues, in green
335 color, are shown in Figure S3B). The relevant functional groups that are predicted by DFT
336 (Figure S1; Supporting Information) are in agreement with the functional groups involved in
337 hydrogen bonding and π - π interactions with the CYP17A1 enzyme by molecular docking
338 (Figure S3; Supporting Information).

339 The binding mode for NCE **1** is similar to the binding mode of endogenous substrates
340 of CYP17A1 enzyme such as pregnenolone, progesterone, 17 α -hydroxypregnenolone, and
341 17 α -hydroxyprogesterone. These endogenous substrates undergo type I inhibition, where an
342 active site water as a sixth ligand is displaced from the heme coordination during the catalytic
343 cycle [19,25,40,50]. On the contrary, the binding mode of NCE **1** is different from the binding
344 mode observed for TOK001 and ABT [23], which shows type II inhibition, where their metal
345 binding groups undergoes metal coordination with ferric heme. NCE **1** also shows a hydrogen
346 bond between its OH group and the carbonyl group of ASN202 [50]. This interaction is also
347 observed in the binding mode found here for TOK001 (see Figure S2B in Supporting
348 Information).

349 After visual inspection of the poses for the NCEs on the enzyme cavity of 3SWZ, it was
350 decided to select 12 NCEs (satisfying the filtering criteria) as well as some derivatives from
351 the skeleton of one NCE. Only the synthesis of structures shown in Table 2 as new chemical
352 entities (NCEs) was feasible. They include eight NCEs (**1-8**) and five derivatives from the
353 skeleton of NCE **8** yielding (NCEs **8a** to **8e**).

354

355 **Table 2.** Hit structures that were synthesized as new chemical entities (NCEs) with their IUPAC

356 names

Name	2D Structure and IUPAC name
1	<p>((R)-2-(2-((2-(1H-indol-3-yl)-2-oxo-1-phenylethyl)thio)-4-methylthiazol-5-yl)acetamide)</p>
2	<p>N-[(2-chlorophenyl)methyl]-2-({4-[(furan-2-yl)methyl]-5-(1H-indol-3-yl)-4H-1,2,4-triazol-3-yl} sulfanyl)acetamide</p>
3	<p>N-(4-ethylphenyl)-5-(2-hydroxy-5-methoxybenzoyl)-2-imino-2H-pyran-3-carboxamide</p>
4	<p>2-(4-sulfamoylphenoxy)ethyl 2-amino-3-methylbenzoate</p>

5

N-(3-[[carbamoyl(phenyl)methyl]amino]phenyl)-2-methoxypropanamide

6

1-(4-butanamidophenyl)-1-oxopropan-2-yl-1H-indazole-3-carboxylate

7

N-(2-hydroxyphenyl)-4-{3-[(2-hydroxyphenyl)carbamoyl]phenoxy}benzamide

Acetamide Heterocycle = 2-chlorobenzamide;

$R_1 = \text{Cl}$; $R_2 = \text{H}$

8a Acetamide Heterocycle = N-(pyridin-3-yl)acetamide;

$R_1 = \text{OH}$; $R_2 = \text{H}$

8b Acetamide Heterocycle = N-(pyridin-3-yl)acetamide;

$R_1 = \text{H}$; $R_2 = \text{H}$

8c Acetamide Heterocycle = N-(2-hydroxyphenyl)acetamide;

$R_1 = \text{H}$; $R_2 = \text{H}$

8d Acetamide Heterocycle = 1H-pyrazole-4-carboxamide;

$R_1 = \text{H}$; $R_2 = \text{Cl}$

8e Acetamide Heterocycle = N-(pyridin-3-yl)acetamide;

$R_1 = \text{Cl}$; $R_2 = \text{H}$

358 The molecules **8a** to **8e** are derivatives from the hit **8** skeleton.

359

360 2.6. Biological activities

361 The NCEs in Table 2 were investigated as possible inhibitors of the 17 α -hydroxylase
362 and lyase activities of human CYP17A1, using pregnenolone and 17 α -hydroxypregnenolone
363 as substrates, respectively. Chromatograms for the corresponding measured metabolites (17 α -
364 hydroxypregnenolone and DHEA, respectively) and the IS (imipramine) are shown in Figure
365 S4 in the Supporting Information. It is difficult to judge and compare the IC_{50} values of novel
366 inhibitors because of the differences in the experimental conditions of assays. For instance, the
367 inhibition of the hydroxylase route of AA has provided *in vitro* IC_{50} values ranging from 1.7
368 nM [13] to 201 nM [23]. Furthermore, in the literature different substrates have been used such
369 as pregnenolone [13] and progesterone [23] in the assays for CYP17A1 inhibition. **The**
370 **hydroxylase vs. lyase assay uses human CYP17A1 extracted from E. Coli. This means that the**
371 **IC_{50} values obtained in this work could differ from those obtained using CYP17A1 enzymes**
372 **extracted from mammalian species such as adrenals and mammalian cells expressing**
373 **CYP17A1 and cytochrome b5, as in [24].** Thus, the use of negative and positive control
374 inhibitors (e.g. ketoconazole and AA, respectively) has been suggested for comparison
375 purposes [19,25,50]. In this work, AA was assayed, in parallel to the NCEs under study, as a
376 positive control inhibitor in the CYP17A1 hydroxylase and lyase assay, respectively. Table 3
377 shows the half-maximal inhibitory concentrations (IC_{50} -values in μ M units) determined for the
378 NCEs and AA, as well as literature results for AA for comparison [13,19,33,51-53]. Individual
379 dose-response curves can be found in the supporting information (Table S3). As can be
380 observed, IC_{50} -values for AA are reasonable comparable to those in the literature; which
381 validate the method used. NCEs with $IC_{50} > 160 \mu$ M were considered to provide null inhibition.

382

383 **Table 3.** Experimental IC_{50} values (in μ M units; mean from duplicate assays) for the synthesized new
 384 chemical entities (NCEs) in Table 2 and abiraterone (AA; positive inhibition control) against human
 385 CYP17A1 hydroxylase and lyase routes and lyase:hydroxylase selectivity. For ABT, literature results
 386 are also included.

NCE (in Table 2)	IC_{50} -hydroxylase	IC_{50} -lyase	Lyase:hydroxylase selectivity	Reference
1	80.5	32.9	2.4	This work
2	n.i.	*	-	
3	n.i.	n.i.	-	
4	n.i.	*	-	
5	n.i.	n.i.	-	
6	n.i.	n.i.	-	
7	n.i.	141	Poor	
8	n.i.	135	Poor	
8a	n.i.	61.4	High	
8b	n.i.	n.i.	-	
8c	88.8	35.4	2.5	
8d	n.i.	156	Poor	
8e	n.i.	n.i.	-	
ABT (positive control)	0.017	0.008	2.1	This work

0.0017	0.0153	0.1	13
0.0025	0.015	0.2	19
0.092	0.036	2.6	33
0.004	0.0025	1.6	51
0.025	0.016	1.6	51
0.030	0.027	1.1	52
0.007	0.012	0.6	53

387 * IC_{50} not determined since the inhibition did not decrease with increased inhibitor concentration. n.i.:
388 160 μ M was fixed as the maximum assay concentration (this IC_{50} value was considered as null
389 inhibition, n.i.). The lyase:hydroxylase selectivity was calculated as the IC_{50} -hydroxylase / IC_{50} -lyase
390 ratio.

391 NCE **1** shows partial inhibitory activity at mid- μ M level for hydroxylase and lyase
392 routes (IC_{50} of 80.5 and 32.9 μ M, respectively). Unfortunately, it was synthesized as a racemic
393 mixture (due to experimental difficulties related to asymmetric synthesis and optical resolution
394 methods), instead of synthesizing the (R)-enantiomer as suggested by resulting docking pose
395 (Figure S3B; Supporting Information). Regarding the synthesized derivatives, only NCE **8a**
396 and **8c** showed inhibitory activity at mid- μ M level for CYP17A1 lyase inhibition. NCE **8a**
397 showed null inhibition and $IC_{50} = 61.4 \mu$ M for hydroxylase and lyase inhibition, respectively
398 (a very important combination in terms of selectivity/security of an anti-mCRPC drug). The
399 real interest of Table 3 is to explore the lyase:hydroxylase selectivity (as the IC_{50} -hydroxylase
400 / IC_{50} - lyase ratio). NCEs **1** and **8c** shows noticeable selectivity (around 2.5) while **8a** shows a
401 high selectivity, becoming virtually specific for the lyase route. In contrast to NCE **8a**, for
402 NCEs **7**, **8** and **8d**, the value of IC_{50} for the lyase inhibition is too close to the limit (160 μ M)

403 and their selectivity becomes *a priori* poor. As before, the selectivity result for AA in this work
404 (2.1) is reasonable comparable to some favorable selectivity data to lyase route reported
405 previously (validating the methodology).

406 An explanation for the selectivity of NCE **1** over other NCEs could be attributed to the
407 presence of the indole moiety of the ligand as well as the acetamide moiety. For **8a**, the unique
408 lyase activity could be attributed to the inclusion of an OH group in R₁ as well as the presence
409 of N-(pyridin-3-yl)acetamide heterocycle (see Table 3). The superior lyase inhibitory potency
410 over the hydroxylase of NCE **8c** could be attributed to the inclusion of N-(2-
411 hydroxyphenyl)acetamide heterocycle to the core-structure (see Table 3). This is consistent
412 with the observations made by Bonomo et al.[33], who indicated that the presence of N-
413 heterocycles on the ligand when it binds with the CYP17A1 enzyme improves the binding
414 affinity. In contrast, the chloro group in either R₁ or R₂ on the skeleton structure of the
415 derivatives seems to reduce *IC*₅₀ values for both lyase and hydroxylase activities (see Table 3).

416 It is difficult (but desirable) to try to connect docking outputs to experimental values,
417 and just hypothesis can be defined. Such hypothesis could be used to plan further optimization
418 stages. As a hypothesis, in the case of NCE **8a**, the introduction of an OH group as R₁ in the
419 skeleton of hit **8** (not present in other derivatives of Table 2) could be related to the high lyase
420 selectivity. Docking outputs revealed that this OH group forms simultaneously two hydrogen
421 bonds (ARG239 and ASP298 residues; Figure S5 in Supporting Information). Also, as
422 hypothesis, in the case of NCE **8c**, the introduction of the N-(2-hydroxyphenyl)acetamide
423 group in the skeleton of hit **8** (not present in other derivatives of Table 2) could be related to
424 the lyase selectivity. Docking outputs indicates a strong hydrogen bond between the OH group
425 of N-(2-hydroxyphenyl) as the hydrogen bond donor and the carbonyl group of VAL482 as the
426 hydrogen bond acceptor Figure S6 in Supporting Information), with a bond radius of 1.61Å
427 (the strongest interaction found for NCEs in Table 2).

428 The IC_{50} values of NCE **1**, **8a** and **8c** (μM level) are higher than those for the control
429 are (ABT; nM level). However, compared to this control, these three NCEs present a higher
430 selectivity value (Table 3) with the method used in this work. These results are adequate enough
431 to consider these NCEs as leads compounds for further optimization to yield nM lyase
432 inhibitors. In our opinion, such novel chemical scaffolds could be useful to design drugs that
433 do not succumb to MES (due to hydroxylase route inhibition), as occurs with ABT. Particularly,
434 NCE **8a** seems to be ineffective to inhibit the hydroxylase route according to the current
435 experimental conditions (Table 3), which is the most promising fact.

436 Unfortunately, the clinical success of a compound cannot be extrapolated from its *in*
437 *vitro* lyase selectivity. Reported IC_{50} values for hydroxylase:lyase inhibition of TOK001 (73
438 and 23 nM, respectively [24]), indicates a selectivity of 3.1 (higher than for AA; selectivity \sim 2).
439 However, the clinical trials for TOK001 have been halted, since there are no observed
440 therapeutic benefits of TOK001 that outweighs those of AA [31-34]. Reported IC_{50} values for
441 hydroxylase:lyase inhibition of VT-464 (670 and 69 nM, respectively [24]), indicates a
442 selectivity of 9.8; although its clinical success is still unknown (Phase II stage). The current
443 selectivity of NCE **1** and **8c** is only slightly higher than AA, selectivity \sim 2.5 (Table 3). A
444 potential higher selectivity is expected for NCE **8a**, since it shows null hydroxylase inhibition
445 (i.e. potentially specific for the lyase route). On the other hand, these NCEs can still be
446 optimized in order to attain nM inhibition and higher lyase selectivity values, thus they could
447 be considered promising candidate structures.

448 Further strategies to optimize the three NCEs found could include the following: (i) to
449 separate the R and S enantiomers and measure their hydroxylase and lyase inhibition. (ii) to
450 synthesize and test the tentative structures of major metabolites of the NCEs; that could be
451 obtained by the Phase I & II metabolism of them on human hepatocytes. The tentative
452 structures of the major metabolites could be elucidated from UHPLC-MS/MS experiment. The

453 aim would be to evaluate their binding to CYP17A1 enzyme in the hydroxylase and lyase
454 routes by the proposed method; (iii) to design derivatives of these NCEs by altering their
455 functional groups using R group enumeration panel on Schrödinger suite and free energy
456 perturbation (FEP+) [54]; (iv) to perform hit expansion, bioisostere replacement/addition and
457 further relative binding affinity prediction with (FEP+) [54-58]. FEP+ essentially works by
458 predicting the relative binding affinities of compounds with known IC_{50} values obtained in
459 similar experimental conditions.

460

461 3. CONCLUSIONS

462 A 3D-QSAR pharmacophore model was able to predict, with a reliability level of 90 %
463 (predictive ability), the inhibitory activity of 78 CYP17A1 non-steroidal inhibitors sourced
464 from the literature (with diverse *in vitro* IC_{50} data and chemical classes). The optimum
465 pharmacophore hypothesis has two hydrogen bond acceptors, two hydrogen bond donors and
466 two aromatic rings groups. They represent non-steroidal structures but not steroidal ones. It
467 allowed screening 2.5 million structures to get the best hits. Density functional theory and
468 docking calculations provided clues on the structure-activity relationships and binding modes.
469 Eight highly active hits, plus five derivatives of one of them, were synthesized as new chemical
470 entities (NCEs). *In vitro* IC_{50} values for the CYP17A1 hydroxylase and lyase inhibition routes
471 demonstrated selectivity to the lyase route of three NCEs (better than abiraterone). One of them
472 showed null inhibition for the hydroxylase route (indispensable to avoid the undesirable use of
473 prednisone). They still fail in *in vitro* inhibitory activity (μ M level). However, they should
474 serve as starting point of designing/optimizing/synthesizing new potent selective CYP17A1
475 17,20-lyase inhibitors based on different chemical scaffolds from the currently used in the
476 clinic (with reduced success up to now). Such strategy could offer alternative potential
477 therapeutic drugs that could improve the overall survival rates of patients diagnosed with

478 metastatic-castration resistant prostate cancer. Moreover, when the challenge is still to
479 overcome the recent research failures.

480

481

482 5. EXPERIMENTAL SECTION

483 5.1. Chemistry

484 *General:* Melting points were determined on an OptiMelt Automated Melting Point
485 System, Digital Image Processing Technology SRS Stanford Research Systems. NMR spectra
486 were measured on a Bruker Top Spin 3.2 (400 MHz). The solvent used for NMR analysis was
487 CDCl₃ or DMSO-*d*₆ with Tetra Methyl Silane (TMS) as an internal standard. The *J* (coupling
488 constant) values were estimated in Hertz (Hz). Atmospheric pressure chemical ionization
489 (APCI) mass spectra were determined on an Agilent Technologies 1260 Infinity II LC/MSD
490 system with DAD\ELSD G7102A 1290 Infinity II and Agilent LC\MSD G6120B mass-
491 spectrometer. All compounds tested for bioassay had a purity of 95-100%. Abbreviations used
492 are as follows: s = singlet, d = doublet, t = triplet, m = multiplet, br s = broad singlet.

493 5.1.1. Synthetic protocols

494 5.1.1.1. General procedure for method A

495 To a solution of 9.37 mmol of compound **15** in 15 ml of anhydrous ethanol 11.44 mmol
496 of corresponding compound **16** was added at room temperature with stirring. Thin Layer
497 Chromatography (TLC) was used to control the end point of the reaction. The reaction mixture
498 was filtered. The resulting solid was washed with anhydrous ethanol to give 7.665 mmol of
499 yellow solid product that was dissolved in 20 ml anhydrous ethanol. 0.445 g (11.5 mmol, 96%)
500 sodium borohydride was added in portions and stirred for 30 minutes at room temperature. The
501 reaction mixture was poured into ice water, filtered, dried to give products: **8**, **8a-8e**. The yields
502 were 74-92%.

503

504 **5.1.1.2. General procedure for method B**

505 To a solution of compound **15** (99 mg; 600 μmol) in anhydrous dichloromethane (2
506 ml), triethylamine (105 μl , 753 μmol), and compound **17** (170 mg, 600 μmol) in anhydrous
507 dichloromethane (2 ml) were added and the mixture was agitated at room temperature for 14
508 hours. Water was added to the reaction solution and an organic phase was extracted with ethyl
509 acetate. The organic phase was washed with water and saturated aqueous solution of sodium
510 bicarbonate and sodium chloride. The resulting mixture was dried over magnesium sulfate
511 followed by concentration under a reduced pressure. A crude product was purified via silica
512 gel column chromatography using hexane:ethyl acetate (1:1) as an eluting solvent yielding 8d
513 (160 mg, 99%).

514 **5.1.1.3. General procedure for method C**

515 A mixture of 526 mg (2 mmole) 4-oxy-bis-benzoic acid and 3 ml THF and 0.22 ml (2
516 mmole) triethylamine was cooled in an ultra low temperature freezer and then 0.275 ml (2
517 mmol) t-butylchloroformate was added while stirring. The product was cooled again in a
518 freezer and 390 mg (4 mmol) 4-aminoisobutyric acid and 0.5 g sodium hydroxide in 1 ml cold
519 water was added with 2 ml THF. The solution was stirred for 2 hrs, evaporated, cold water was
520 added, and evaporated again to remove the rest of the THF. The product was recrystallized
521 from isopropanol to give **7** as a white powder (yield 0.6 g; 91%). Physical and spectral data are
522 presented below.

523 **5.1.2. ((R/S)-2-(2-((2-(1H-indol-3-yl)-2-oxo-1-phenylethyl)thio)-4-methylthiazol-5-**
524 **yl)acetamide) (NCE1).**

525 A vial was charged with 2-(2-Mercapto-4-methyl-thiazol-5-yl)-acetamide (1.0 equiv.),
526 Dimethyl Formamide (DMF) (2 ml), N,N-Diisopropylethylamine (DIPEA) (1.2 equiv.). To the
527 stirred mixture 2-Chloro-1-(1H-indol-3-yl)-2-phenyl-ethanone (1.0 equiv.) was added. The

528 vial was capped and heated while stirring for 1hr. After 30 minutes, the reaction mixture
529 became clear and heating was continued for further 3hrs. Then the vial was cooled, diluted with
530 water, and a precipitate formed was filtered off, washed with water and dried. The average
531 yield was 20%; mp, 202-203 °C; ¹H-NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-D₆), δ 2.17 (s, -CH₃), 3.44 (s,
532 2H, -CH₂), δ 6.46 (s, -CH), 7.05 (s, 1H, NH₂), 7.16-7.26 (m, 3H, aromatic), 7.30-7.34 (m, 2H,
533 aromatic), 7.44-7.46 (dd, 1H, ³J = 6.18 Hz and ⁴J = 1.40 Hz, aromatic), δ 7.54 (s, 1H, NH₂),
534 7.63-7.65 (m, 2H, aromatic), 8.13-8.15 (dd, 1H, ³J = 6.99 Hz and ⁴J = 2.26 Hz, aromatic), 8.71-
535 8.72 (d, 1H, ³J = 3.15 Hz, indole-H) and 12.15-12.16 (d, 1H, ³J = 2.35 Hz, indole-NH); ¹³C-
536 NMR (100 MHz, DMSO-D₆), δ 15.3, 33.3, 59.0, 112.8, 114.5, 121.7, 122.7, 123.7, 126.1,
537 126.6, 128.5, 128.9, 129.2, 135.9, 137.1, 137.7, 148.9, 158.7, 170.9, 188.9; MS (APCI): m/z =
538 422 [M⁺+H].

539 **5.1.3. N-[(2-chlorophenyl)methyl]-2-({4-[(furan-2-yl)methyl]-5-(1H-indol-3-yl)-4H-1,2,4-
540 triazol-3-yl}sulfanyl)acetamid (NCE2).**

541 A vial was charged with 4-Furan-2-ylmethyl-5-indol-3-ylidene-[1,2,4]triazolidene-3-
542 thione (1.0 equiv.), DMF (2 ml), DIPEA (1.2 equiv.). To the stirred mixture 2-Chloro-N-(2-
543 chloro-benzyl)-acetamide (1.0 equiv.) was added. The vial was capped and heated while
544 stirring for 1hr. After 30 min, the reaction mixture became clear and heating was continued for
545 further 3hrs. Then the vial was cooled, diluted with water, and the precipitate formed was
546 filtered off, washed with water and dried. The average yield was 20%; mp, 184-185 °C; ¹H-
547 NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-D₆), δ 4.03 (s, 2H, -CH₂-S), 4.35-4.36 (d, 2H, ³J = 5.54 Hz, -CH₂-
548 NH), 5.39 (s, 2H, -CH₂-N-triazole), 6.39-6.44 (m, 2H, H-furan), 7.12-7.16 (m, 1H, aromatic),
549 7.19-7.27 (m, 3H, aromatic), 7.33-7.35 (m, 1H, aromatic), 7.38-7.41 (m, 1H, aromatic), 7.49-
550 7.51 (d, 1H, ³J = 8.18 Hz, aromatic), 7.63-7.64 (m, 1H, aromatic), 7.91 (s, 1H, indole C-H),
551 8.05-8.07 (d, 1H, ³J = 7.90 Hz, aromatic), 8.81-8.84 (t, 1H, ³J = 6.14 Hz, NH-amide), 11.76 (s,
552 1H, N-H-indole); ¹³C-NMR (100 MHz, DMSO-D₆), δ 37.4, 79.6, 101.6, 109.6, 111.2, 112.3,

553 120.7, 121.3, 122.9, 125.9, 126.2, 127.6, 129.1, 129.3, 129.5, 132.4, 136.3, 136.4, 144.0, 148.9,
554 149.5, 151.9, 167.8; MS (APCI): $m/z = 478 [M^+ + H]$.

555 **5.1.4. N-(4-ethylphenyl)-5-(2-hydroxy-5-methoxybenzoyl)-2-imino-2H-pyran-3-**
556 **carboxamide (NCE3).**

557 The reaction was carried out in 8 ml glass vial. The reactants were loaded in view that
558 1.0 equivalent is equal to 0.75 mmol of the compound. A vial was charged with 6-Methoxy-4-
559 oxo-4H-chromene-3-carbaldehyde (1.0 equiv.) and corresponding 2-Cyano-N-(4-ethyl-
560 phenyl)-acetamide active compound (1.0 equiv.), acetic acid (5 ml), and sodium acetate (1.1
561 equiv.). The vial was capped and heated at 100 °C for 8hrs. Then it was cooled and diluted with
562 water (5 ml). The formed precipitate was filtered, dried, and re-crystallized from acetonitrile.
563 The yield was 48%; mp, 132-133 °C; ¹H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃), δ 1.25-1.29 (t, 3H, ³J =
564 7.68 Hz, -CH₃), 2.69-2.74 (q, 2H, ³J = 7.68 Hz, -CH₂), 3.77 (s, 3H, -OCH₃), 6.95-6.69 (d, 1H,
565 ⁴J = 2.94 Hz, aromatic), 7.02-7.04 (d, 1H, ³J = 9.00 Hz, aromatic), 7.15-7.18 (dd, 1H, ³J = 9.14
566 Hz and ⁴J = 3.09 Hz, aromatic), 7.27-7.30 (m, 2H, aromatic), 7.34-7.37 (m, 2H, aromatic),
567 8.22-8.23 (d, 1H, ⁴J = 2.65 Hz, C-H pyranimine), 8.30-8.31 (d, 1H, ⁴J = 2.65 Hz, C-H
568 pyranimine), 10.67 (s, 1H, NH-amide); ¹³C-NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃), δ 15.3, 28.5, 55.9, 106.0,
569 114.0, 114.4, 116.6, 117.8, 120.0, 124.3, 125.7, 129.3, 136.4, 146.6, 146.8, 147.3, 151.9, 156.7,
570 158.6, 192.7; MS (APCI): $m/z = 395 [M^+ + H]$.

571 **5.1.5. 2-(4-sulfamoylphenoxy)ethyl 2-amino-3-methylbenzoate (NCE 4).**

572 The reaction was carried out in 8 ml glass vial. The reactants were loaded in view that
573 1.0 equivalent is equal to 1.4 mmol of the compound. A vial was charged with 2-Amino-3-
574 methyl-benzoic acid (1.2 equiv.), DMF (2 ml), and DIPEA (1.2 equiv.). To the stirred mixture
575 in the vial, 4-(2-Bromo-ethoxy)-benzenesulfonamide (1.0 equiv.) was added. The vial was
576 capped and heated under stirring for 1hr. After 30 min the reaction mixture became clear and

577 heating was continued for further 6hrs at 100 °C. Then the vial was cooled, diluted with water,
578 and extracted with chloroform. The combined organic layers were dried over concentrated
579 sodium sulfate. The crude product was purified with CombiFlash chromatography on silica gel.
580 The average yield was 50%; mp, 165-166 °C; ¹H-NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-D₆) δ 2.10 (s, 3H,
581 -CH₃), 4.39-4.41 (t, 2H, ³J = 7.60 Hz, -CH₂), 4.54-4.56 (t, 2H, ³J = 7.60 Hz, -CH₂), 6.46-6.49
582 (m, 2H, aromatic CH and NH₂), 7.14-7.19 (m, 3H, aromatic), 7.24 (s, 2H, Ar-NH₂), 7.59-7.61
583 (dd, 1H, ³J = 8.13 Hz and ⁴J = 1.05 Hz, aromatic), 7.73-7.75 (m, 2H, aromatic); ¹³C-NMR (100
584 MHz, DMSO-D₆), δ 18.1, 62.8, 66.8, 108.8, 115.1, 123.8, 128.2, 129.0, 135.4, 136.9, 150.1,
585 161.1, 168.2; MS (APCI): m/z = 351 [M⁺+H].

586 **5.1.6. N-(3-{{carbamoyl(phenyl)methyl}amino}phenyl)-2-methoxypropanamide (NCE5).**

587 The reaction was carried out in 8 ml glass vial. The reactants were loaded in view that
588 1.0 equivalent is equal to 1.8 mmol of the compound. To a stirred solution containing specified
589 amounts of m-aminophenyl-2-methoxypropanamide (1.0 equiv.), DIPEA (1.1 equiv.), and
590 potassium iodide (catalyst) in 1 ml of DMF and benzylchloridemethanamide (1.0 equiv.) was
591 added. The reaction mixture was allowed to stir on a boiling water bath for 5 min. Upon
592 complete dissolution of the reagents the stirred reaction mixture was heated on the water bath
593 for further 6hrs. The reaction mixture was saturated with an excess of deionized water and
594 sonicated until a crystalline precipitate was formed. The precipitate was filtered, washed twice
595 with methanol, and dried. The crude product was purified by chromatography (silica gel,
596 CHCl₃:iPrOH = 4:1). The yield was 30%; mp, 167-168 °C; ¹H-NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-D₆),
597 δ 1.26-1.27 (d, 3H, ³J = 6.63 Hz, -CH₃), 3.26 (s, 3H, -CH₃), 3.79-3.84 (q, 1H, ³J = 6.81 Hz, -
598 CH), 4.88-4.89 (d, 1H, ³J = 5.29 Hz, -CH), 6.06-6.07 (d, 1H, ³J = 7.19 Hz, aromatic), 6.36-6.38
599 (d, 1H, ³J = 7.19 Hz, aromatic), 6.82-6.84 (m, 1H, aromatic), 6.92-6.97 (m, 1H, aromatic), 7.06
600 (s, 1H, -NH₂), 7.20 (s, 1H, -NH₂), 7.23-7.27 (m, 1H, aromatic), 7.31-7.35 (m, 2H, aromatic),
601 7.49-7.52 (m, 2H, aromatic), 7.71 (s, 1H, amide N-H), 9.51-9.53 (d, 1H, ³J = 5.11 Hz, amide

602 N-H); ^{13}C -NMR (100 MHz, DMSO- D_6), δ 18.8, 57.1, 60.8, 79.6, 104.9, 105.0, 108.9, 109.4,
603 127.7, 127.9, 128.7, 129.2, 139.6, 140.2, 147.9, 171.3, 173.1 MS (APCI): m/z = 328 [M^+H].

604 **5.1.7. 1-(4-butanamidophenyl)-1-oxopropan-2-yl-1H-indazole-3-carboxylate (NCE6)**

605 The reaction was carried out in 8 ml glass vial. The reactants were loaded in view that
606 1.0 equivalent is equal to 1.4 mmol of the compound. A vial was charged with 1H-Indazole-3-
607 carboxylic acid (1.2 equiv.), DMF (2 ml), and DIPEA (1.2 equiv.). To the stirred mixture N-
608 [4-(2-Chloro-propionyl)-phenyl]-butyramide (1.0 equiv.) was added. The vial was capped and
609 heated under stirring for an 1hr. After 30 minutes, the reaction mixture became clear and
610 heating was continued for the next 6hrs at 100 °C. Then the vial was cooled, diluted with water,
611 and extracted with chloroform. The combined organic layers were dried over concentrated
612 sodium sulfate. The crude product was purified with CombiFlash chromatography on silica gel.
613 The average yield was 50%; mp, 205-206 °C; ^1H -NMR (400 MHz, DMSO- D_6) δ 0.91-0.94 (t,
614 3H, ^3J = 7.36 Hz, - CH_3), 1.63-1.67 (m, 5H, - CH_2 and - CH_3), 2.32-2.36 (t, 2H, ^3J = 7.46 Hz, -
615 CH_2), 6.31-6.41 (q, 1H, ^3J = 6.86 Hz, -CH), 7.32-7.36 (m, 1H, aromatic), 7.46-7.50 (m, 1H,
616 aromatic), 7.69-7.71 (d, 1H, ^3J = 8.23 Hz, aromatic), 7.79-7.81 (d, 2H, ^3J = 8.85 Hz, aromatic),
617 8.05-8.09 (m, 3H, aromatic), 10.31 (s, 1H, -NH), 14.04 (s, 1H, -COOH): ^{13}C -NMR (100 MHz,
618 DMSO- D_6), δ 14.1, 17.8, 18.9, 72.1, 111.7, 118.9, 121.4, 122.7, 123.5, 127.2, 128.6, 130.3,
619 135.0, 141.4, 144.8, 161.9, 172.4, 195.5; MS (APCI): m/z = 380 [M^+H].

620 **5.1.8. N-(2-hydroxyphenyl)-4-{3-[(2-hydroxyphenyl)carbamoyl]phenoxy}benzamide** 621 **(NCE7).**

622 NCE 7 was synthesized by using the general procedure in method C; mp, 266-267 °C;
623 ^1H -NMR (400 MHz, DMSO- d_6) δ 6.81-6.85 (m, 2H, aromatic), 6.91-6.93 (dd, 2H, ^3J = 8.06
624 Hz and ^4J = 1.27 Hz aromatic), 7.01-7.06 (m, 2H, aromatic), 7.20-7.22 (m, 4H, aromatic), 7.64-
625 7.66 (dd, 2H, ^3J = 8.06 Hz and ^4J = 1.27 Hz, aromatic), 8.04-8.07 (m, 4H, aromatic) Hz δ 9.56

626 (s, 2H, -NH-amide); ¹³C-NMR (100 MHz, DMSO-D₆), δ 116.5, 119.1, 119.4, 124.8, 126.2,
627 126.3, 130.3, 130.4, 150.0, 159.2, 164.9; MS (APCI): m/z = 340 [M⁺+H].

628 **5.1.9. 2-chloro-N-(3-{{(6-chloro-3-oxo-3,4-dihydro-2H-1,4-benzoxazin-7-**
629 **yl)amino}methyl}phenyl)benzamide (NCE8).**

630 NCE 8 was synthesized by using the general procedure for method B; mp, 231-232 °C;
631 ¹H-NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-D₆) δ 4.36 (s, 2H, -CH₂-N and 2°), 4.42 (s, 2H, -CH₂-O), 4.45 (s,
632 1H, 2° amine N-H) 6.14 (s, 1H, aromatic), 6.82 (s, 1H, aromatic), 7.08-7.09 (m, 1H, aromatic),
633 7.27-7.31 (m, 1H, aromatic), 7.42-7.74 (m, 6H, aromatic), 10.41 (s, 1H, amide N-H), 10.50 (s,
634 1H, amide N-H); ¹³C-NMR (100 MHz, DMSO-D₆), δ 67.3, 79.7, 100.5, 103.6, 110.6, 111.1,
635 116.5, 122.7, 127.9, 129.3, 129.4, 130.1, 130.6, 131.5, 137.6, 139.8, 140.7, 141.2, 143.8, 164.2,
636 165.4; MS (APCI): m/z = 443 [M⁺+H].

637 **5.1.10. 3-{{(6-hydroxy-3-oxo-3,4-dihydro-2H-1,4-benzoxazin-7-yl)amino}methyl}-N-**
638 **(pyridin-3-yl)benzamide (NCE8a).**

639 NCE 8a was synthesized by using the general procedure for method A; mp, 231-232
640 °C; ¹H-NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-D₆) δ 4.39 (s, 2H, -CH₂-N), 4.45 (s, 2H, -CH₂-O), 4.50 (s, 1H,
641 2° amine N-H), 6.54 (s, 2H, aromatic), 7.55-7.59 (m, 1H, aromatic), 7.65-7.67 (m, 1H,
642 aromatic), 7.94-8.11 (m, 3H, aromatic), 8.56-8.64 (m, 2H, aromatic), 9.34-9.35 (d, 1H, ⁴J =
643 2.08 Hz, pyridine-H), 10.56 (s, 1H, amide N-H), 11.23 (s, 1H, amide N-H); MS (APCI): m/z =
644 391 [M⁺+H].

645

646 **5.1.11. 3-{[(3-oxo-3,4-dihydro-2H-1,4-benzoxazin-7-yl)amino]methyl}-N-(pyridin-3-**
647 **yl)benzamide (NCE 8b).**

648 NCE 8b was synthesized by using the general procedure for method A; mp, 118-119
649 °C; ¹H-NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-D₆) δ 4.29-4.30 (d, 2H, ³J = 5.45 Hz, -CH₂-NH), 4.41 (s, 2H,
650 -CH₂-O), 6.17-6.25 (m, 2H, aromatic), 6.59-6.13 (d, 1H, ³J = 8.33 Hz, aromatic), 7.34-7.41 (m,
651 1H, aromatic), 7.47-7.51 (m, 1H, aromatic), 7.56-7.58 (1H, d, ³J = 7.78 Hz, aromatic), 7.83-
652 7.85 (d, 1H, ³J = 7.63 Hz, aromatic), 7.94 (s, 1H, aromatic), 8.17-8.19 (m, 1H, pyridine-H),
653 8.30-8.32 (m, 1H, aromatic), 8.92 (d, 1H, ⁴J = 2.31 Hz, pyridine-H), 10.31 (s, 1H, amide N-H),
654 10.47 (s, 1H, amide N-H); ¹³C-NMR (100 MHz, DMSO-D₆), δ 67.2, 79.6, 100.7, 106.8, 116.7,
655 123.7, 126.9, 127.0, 127.7, 128.8, 130.9, 134.8, 136.2, 141.3, 142.4, 144.6, 144.9, 145.5, 164.3,
656 166.3; MS (APCI): m/z = 375 [M⁺+H].

657 **5.1.12. N-(2-hydroxyphenyl)-3-{[(3-oxo-3,4-dihydro-2H-1,4-benzoxazin-7-**
658 **yl)amino]methyl}benzamide (NCE 8c).**

659 NCE 8c was synthesized by using the general procedure of method A; 192-193 °C; ¹H-
660 NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-D₆) δ 4.28-4.29 (d, 2H, ³J = 5.67 Hz, -CH₂-NH), 4.40 (s, 2H, -CH₂-
661 O), 6.18-6.27 (m, 2H, aromatic), 6.59-6.61 (d, 1H, ³J = 8.36 Hz, aromatic), 6.73-6.82 (m, 1H,
662 aromatic), 6.89-6.92 (dd, 1H, ³J = 7.99 Hz and ⁴J = 1.23 Hz, aromatic), 7.04-7.09 (m, 1H,
663 aromatic), 7.44-7.48 (m, 1H, aromatic), 7.53-7.55 (d, 1H, ³J = 7.60 Hz, aromatic), 7.67-7.69
664 (d, 1H, ³J = 7.78 Hz, aromatic), 7.81-7.82 (d, 1H, ³J = 7.60 Hz, aromatic), 9.49 (s, 1H, amide
665 N-H), 10.29 (s, 1H, amide N-H); ¹³C-NMR (100 MHz, DMSO-D₆), δ 67.3, 79.8, 100.8, 106.9,
666 116.4, 116.8, 117.2, 119.4, 126.1, 126.3, 126.8, 128.9, 130.9, 134.9, 141.4, 144.7, 145.6, 164.3,
667 165.7; MS (APCI): m/z = 390 [M⁺+H].

668

669 **5.1.13. N-{4-chloro-3-[(3-oxo-3,4-dihydro-2H-1,4-benzoxazin-7-yl)carbamoyl]phenyl}-**
670 **1H-pyrazole-4-carboxamide (NCE8d).**

671 NCE 8d was synthesized by using the general procedure for method B; mp, 308-309
672 °C; ¹H-NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-d₆) δ 4.56 (s, 2H, -CH₂-O), 6.85-6.87 (d, 1H, ³J = 8.48 Hz,
673 aromatic), 7.26-7.29 (dd, 1H, ³J = 8.01 Hz and ⁴J = 2.18 Hz, aromatic), 7.39-7.40 (d, 1H, ⁴J =
674 2.18 Hz, aromatic), 7.50-7.52 (d, 1H, ³J = 8.75 Hz, aromatic), 7.86-7.89 (m, 2H, aromatic),
675 8.07 (s, 1H, pyrazole-H), 8.38 (s, 1H, pyrazole-H), 10.06 (s, 1H, amide N-H), 10.49 (s, 1H,
676 amide N-H), 10.69 (s, 1H, amide N-H), 10.33 (s, 1H, pyrazole N-H); ¹³C-NMR (100 MHz,
677 DMSO-D₆), δ 62.3, 108.3, 114.0, 116.2, 118.0, 120.0, 122.3, 123.7, 123.8, 130.4, 134.7, 137.3,
678 138.8, 143.6, 161.1, 164.9, 165.0; MS (APCI): m/z = 412 [M⁺+H].

679 **5.1.14. 3-[(6-chloro-3-oxo-3,4-dihydro-2H-1,4-benzoxazin-7-yl)amino]methyl}-N-**
680 **(pyridin-3-yl)benzamide (NCE8e).**

681 NCE 8e was synthesized by using the general procedure for method A; mp, 230-231
682 °C; ¹H-NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-D₆), δ 4.42(s, 2H, -CH₂-N), 4.44 (s, 2H, -CH₂-O), 6.13 (s,
683 1H, aromatic), 6.79 (s, 1H, aromatic), 7.38-7.41 (dd, 1H, ³J = 7.89 Hz and ³J = 4.68 Hz,
684 aromatic), 7.48-7.56 (m, 2H, aromatic), 7.83-7.84 (d, 1H, ³J = 7.69 Hz, aromatic), 7.92 (s, 1H,
685 aromatic), 8.16-8.19 (m, 1H, aromatic), 8.30-8.31 (dd, 1H, ³J = 4.68 Hz and ⁴J = 1.43 Hz,
686 pyridine-H), 8.90-8.91 (d, 1H, ⁴J = 2.17 Hz, pyridine-H), 10.41 (s, 1H, amide N-H), 10.48 (s,
687 1H, amide N-H); ¹³C-NMR (100 MHz, DMSO-D₆), δ 67.2, 79.6, 100.5, 111.0, 124.0, 126.5,
688 126.9, 127.8, 128.9, 135.0, 136.2, 140.4, 140.9, 142.4, 143.6, 145.0, 164.2, 166.5; MS (APCI):
689 m/z = 409 [M⁺+H].

690

691 **5.2. Computational Data**

692 Table 1 shows the 78 studied inhibitors. They have ten different core structures (Class)
693 and exhibit broad inhibition activity to CYP17A1 enzyme (*in vitro* experimental IC_{50} between
694 13 to 20000 nM collected from the literature [2, 9, 13, 19, 28, 42-43]. The IC_{50} values in molar
695 units were converted into pIC_{50} data for 3D-QSAR partial least squares (PLS) modeling
696 purposes. The inhibitors (in decreasing order of pIC_{50}) are named as in the original references.
697 They were randomly divided into 63 training (subset 1) and 15 test (subset 2) compounds for
698 model validation.

699 **5.2.1. Computational software program**

700 Maestro (v10.2) [59], a graphical user interface (GUI) in Schrödinger Suite 2015, was
701 used to perform all simulation tasks. The GUI has built-in workflows for all Schrödinger
702 modules in the suite. Conformational searches were performed by using MacroModel (v10.8)
703 [60]. Pharmacophore modeling was performed by using PHASE (v4.3) [61-63], a module of
704 the Schrödinger suite. A virtual Screening Workflow, VSW [64], was employed on the
705 database hit compounds. Quantum mechanical/molecular mechanics calculations (Density
706 functional theory, DFT) were done by using Jaguar (v8.8) [65]. Cross-docking was used to
707 validate docking methods. Cross-docking was performed by using the Glide cross-docking
708 script with default parameters. Compounds that survived the virtual screening procedure were
709 subjected to Induced Fit Docking (IFD) [66]. IFD was used for all flexible molecular docking
710 calculations of database hits screened.

711 **5.2.2. Preparation of structures**

712 The inhibitors were introduced into the PHASE software as 2D structures and converted
713 into 3D formats. Tautomers were generated for low-energy structures at pH 7.4 and every
714 combination of stereoisomers was generated (Ligprep module). The 3D structures were then

715 subjected to a conformational search (MacroModel). OPLS-2005 force-field was used to
716 generate low-energy multiple conformers with a constant dielectric constant of 1.0. The
717 number of minimization steps was set to 100. An energy change of 10 kcal/mol was set for
718 saving multiple conformers. A root-mean-square-deviation (RMSD) cut-off of 1.0 Å was set
719 to eliminate unnecessary conformers.

720 **5.2.3. Pharmacophore modeling**

721 The resulting conformers were mapped against fixed chemical features. The
722 pharmacophore features included hydrogen bond acceptors (A), hydrogen bond donors (D),
723 negatively charged groups (N), positively charged groups (P), hydrophobic groups (H) and
724 aromatic rings (R). The development of the pharmacophore model was performed according
725 to previously reported information [45,46]. Briefly, the search spanned different families of
726 pharmacophores. The number of site points on the data set was six, taken from the 12 most
727 active inhibitors in the training set (Table 1; $IC_{50} < 40$ nM). The best common pharmacophore
728 hypothesis (CPH) was selected as the one showing the 3D-QSAR PLS model with the best
729 prediction ability (i.e. the one showing the highest determination coefficient for the training
730 and test compounds, R^2 and Q^2 respectively). The conformer with the highest fitness score
731 (matching degree between the molecule and the best CPH) was selected as reference
732 compound.

733 **5.2.4. Preparation of a 3D database and pharmacophore screening**

734 A structural database was prepared prior to using the 3D-QSAR model for database
735 screening. 2.5 million drug-like structures were downloaded from the Enamine LTD database
736 [67] and added into the Manage 3D Database panel in PHASE module. The 3D database was
737 prepared by generating ionization states for structures using the PHASE submodule Epik at pH
738 7.4. Structures with high ionization energy and/or high tautomerization states were removed.

739 Structures with undesirable functional groups (from a toxicity point of view) were removed.
740 Furthermore, structures that did not satisfy Lipinski's rule of five were also removed. The 3D-
741 QSAR pharmacophore model was used for database screening. The most active hits (estimated
742 $pIC_{50} > 7$) having the 6 pharmacophore sites of the best CPH were selected for further studies.

743 **5.2.5. Virtual Screening Workflow**

744 A virtual screening workflow, with built in GlideSP and GlideXP was used to screen
745 drug-like molecules from the database. Virtual Screening Workflow provided a reduced
746 number of hit structures after they were screened. Selected hits were submitted to geometry
747 optimization using DFT and further molecular docking using IFD. In the VSW ligand
748 preparation was deselected as the ligands were already prepared during Phase database
749 screening. The remaining ligands were docked on the prepared and minimized structure of
750 3SWZ grid. Glide SP and Glide XP (both built into VSW) were consecutively used. Hits that
751 survived Glide SP were further docked with Glide XP.

752 **5.2.6. Density functional theory calculations**

753 A geometry optimization calculation using a DFT procedure and a basis set function of
754 B3LYP 6-31G* in the Jaguar panel [47,48,65] was used to calculate the electronic properties
755 of the hits. It was then followed by a single-point energy calculation at the optimum geometries
756 to obtain aqueous solution phase energies using a continuum treatment of solvation by Poisson-
757 Boltzmann modeling [48]. The electronic properties of interest calculated included the
758 following: molecular electrostatic potential (MESP), highest occupied and lowest unoccupied
759 molecular orbital (HOMO and LUMO, respectively), and electron density map [47].

760

761 **5.2.7. Cross-docking**

762 Cross-docking was employed to select the suitable PDB structure and to validate the
763 IFD protocol. In cross-docking the co-crystallized ligand of the receptor is removed and then
764 subsequently re-docked into the receptor using Glide/cross-docking script. The main idea is to
765 reproduce the binding mode of the x-ray crystal structure of the protein-ligand complex. The
766 3SWZ and 3RUK PDB X-ray structures, with co-crystallized structures of galeterone and
767 abiraterone, respectively, were tested. The comparison of results from IFD and cross-docking
768 allowed the selection of the PDB enzyme structure for subsequent studies, based on the
769 following criteria: (i) resolution of the enzyme x-ray crystal structure (ii) docking score, (iii)
770 Root Mean Square Deviation (RMSD). Indirectly, the agreement between the outputs served
771 as a validation of the IFD protocol.

772 **5.2.8. Flexible ligand docking with Induced Fit Docking.**

773 A flexible ligand-protein molecular docking procedure was performed using the
774 Glide/IFD protocols [49], since the charges for a free ligand have been previously calculated
775 by a hybrid quantum mechanical calculation (DFT optimization). In this docking protocol, the
776 conformational change of the enzyme and the ligand during binding are accounted for. Since
777 CYP17A1 is a flexible enzyme, it was important to yield conformers close to the real *in vivo*
778 conformation. The drug-like molecules that survived VSW were incorporated into Glide/IFD.
779 The 3SWZ structure (already prepared and minimized) was added. The co-crystallized ligand
780 in the active site cavity of the enzyme was frozen and used to mark the active site of the enzyme;
781 that new compounds need to occupy. Several rules were fixed as filtering criteria for screening
782 hits obtained by IFD: (i) the binding mode of the selected pose should correspond preferably
783 to type I inhibition; since it has been related to a selective lyase inhibition [25]. However, the
784 presence of a metal coordination with ferric heme (type II inhibition) is also allowed; (ii) the
785 ligand pose should possess metal binding groups such as N-containing heterocycles e.g.
786 pyridine rings [19], because N-containing heterocycles form π - π interactions with porphyrin of

787 ferric heme; (iii) a docking score < -6 kcal/mol; (iv) and the presence of a hydrogen bond with
788 ASN202 [23,25]. The hits that satisfied the four criteria were retained.

789 **5.3. Inhibition of NCEs on the hydroxylase and lyase activities of human CYP17A1** 790 **expressed in E.coli bacosomes**

791 The compounds synthesized in section 5.2. above were used for the inhibition of the
792 hydroxylase and lyase activities. The method to estimate IC_{50} values was adapted from [13].

793 **5.3.1. Reagents**

794 Imipramine, abiraterone and pregnenolone were purchased from Santa Cruz
795 Biotechnologies (Heidelberg, Germany), dehydroepiandrosterone (DHEA), magnesium
796 chloride, DMSO and phosphate buffer were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich (Gillingham, UK),
797 ketoconazole was purchased from Sequoia Research Products Ltd. (Pangbourne, UK) and 17 α -
798 hydroxypregnenolone was purchased from Carbosynth (Compton, UK). Co-factors such as
799 nicotinamide adenine dinucleotide phosphate (NADPH), CYP17A1-LR bacosomes and
800 CYP17A1-BR bacosomes were purchased from Cypex (Dundee, UK). HPLC-MS-grade
801 methanol and formic acid were from Fisher Scientific (Loughborough, UK). Water was
802 purified on a Milli Q system (Millipore, Watford, UK).

803 **5.3.2. CYP17A1 hydroxylase and lyase incubations**

804 The CYP17A1 17 α -hydroxylase and lyase inhibition was measured using bacosomes
805 solution. 20 pmol/ml CYP17A1-LR and 10 pmol/ml CYP17A1-BR bacosomes were used for
806 hydroxylase and lyase assays, respectively. Pregnenolone and 17 α -hydroxypregnenolone were
807 used as substrates for hydroxylase and lyase assays, respectively. 1 μ M substrate solution
808 prepared by dilution of the stock solution 10 μ M of pregnenolone and 17 α -
809 hydroxypregnenolone. 1 mM NADPH was prepared in 50 mM potassium phosphate buffer pH
810 7.4 containing 5 mM magnesium chloride. Stock solutions of 16 mM of the synthesized NCEs

811 in DMSO were prepared. In addition, stock solution of 10 mM of ABT as a positive control
812 inhibitor in DMSO was prepared. NCEs and the positive control inhibitor were diluted serially
813 (2.5-fold) in eight steps yielding final assay concentrations of 160 μ M – 0.26 μ M (NCEs) and
814 500 nM to 0.82 nM (positive control inhibitor). Reactions were started by the addition of
815 NADPH and incubated at 37°C for 20 minutes with shaking on a Bioshake IQ (Q-Instruments,
816 Jena, Germany). Reaction volume was 100 μ L and final DMSO concentration was 1 % (v/v).
817 Reactions were terminated by the addition of 300 μ L of methanol containing 25 ng/mL
818 imipramine as an internal standard (IS). The enzyme activity was assessed by measuring the
819 appearance of the corresponding metabolite using UHPLC-MS/MS. Finally, 17 α -
820 hydroxypregnenolone and DHEA were the metabolites obtained, for hydroxylase and lyase
821 assays, respectively. According to the supplier of bacosomes, the CYP17A1-LR used for the
822 hydroxylase experiment contains human CYP17A1 and low human CYP-reductase, thus
823 DHEA formation should be considered negligible. Therefore, 17 α -hydroxypregnenolone was
824 selected as unique analyte to measure the activity of this route. The experiments were
825 performed by means of ultra high performance liquid chromatography-tandem mass
826 spectrometry (UHPLC-MS/MS). All the assays were performed in duplicates.

827 5.3.3. UHPLC-MS/MS analysis

828 A Vanquish UHPLC system (ThermoFisher Scientific, Runcorn, UK) with a binary
829 pump and an autosampler was used. The mobile phase flow rate was 0.8 mL/min and the
830 column temperature was set at 60°C. The injection volume was 3.5 μ L. The separation was
831 performed using an Accucore, (C18, 2.6 μ m, 50 x 2.1 mm, Runcorn, UK) column. The
832 following gradient elution was carried out using different ratios of eluents A (0.1% formic acid
833 in water) and B (0.1% formic acid in methanol): 0-0.69 min, 5 % B; 0.70-1.14 min, 95 % B;
834 1.15 min, 99.9 % B; 1.16-1.40 min, 5 % B for column re-equilibration.

835 A triple quadrupole mass spectrometer (TSQ Quantiva, Thermo Fisher Scientific) with
836 multiple reaction monitoring (MRM) was used for MS detection. The instrument was operated
837 using atmospheric pressure chemical ionisation (APCI) in positive mode. Nitrogen was used
838 as auxiliary and sheath gas, and argon was used as collision gas. The following ion source
839 conditions were used: vaporizer temperature, 500 °C; ion transfer tube temperature, 275 °C;
840 positive ion discharge current, 1 µA; sheath gas, 45 AU; auxiliary gas, 5 AU; sweep gas, 2 AU.
841 The MS/MS parameters were the following: collision gas pressure, 1.5 mTorr; source
842 fragmentation voltage, 0 V; chrom filter, 2 s; and dwell time, 10 ms. The MRM transitions,
843 collision energies and RF lens of the analytes and IS are shown in Table 4. Xcalibur software
844 (v4.0) was used for data analysis.

845

846

847 **Table 4.** Multiple reaction monitoring (MRM) transitions, RF lens and collision energies for LC-
 848 MS/MS measurements

Compound	Precursor (m/z)	Product (m/z)	RF Lens (V)	Collision energy (V)
17 α -Hydroxypregnenolone	315.23	201.10	49	17
		279.15	49	14
		297.17	49	10
Dehydroepiandrosterone (DHEA)	271.23	197.11	51	17
		213.10	51	15
		253.15	51	12
Imipramine (internal standard)	281.13	86.11	50	16
		193.00	50	41
		208.00	50	26

849 **Note:** Mass transitions for each compound were combined to maximize sensitivity.

850 5.3.4. Data Analysis

851 For each sample, the MS response (R) was calculated as the metabolite to IS peak area ratio.

852 The effect (E) was calculated as R in presence of the inhibitor divided by R in absence of it.

853 The IC_{50} values were estimated by fitting the concentration-effect curve data of the inhibitors

854 to a modified version of the Hill equation [68,69].

$$E = \frac{\alpha [I]^{nH}}{[I]^{nH} + IC_{50}^{nH}} \quad (3)$$

856 where E is expressed in percentage, α is the upper asymptotes (maximum effect), $[I]$ is the

857 inhibitor concentration and nH is the Hill slope.

858

859

860 **Supplementary data**

861 Additional tables and figures illustrating statistical data for some 3D-QSAR pharmacophore
862 models, density functional theory results, docking score and root-mean-square-deviation
863 results, docking poses, ligand interaction diagrams and chromatograms.

864

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